

612/E2

A study on physicochemical and antioxidant properties of different brands of 'Nimba Arishta' in Sri Lanka

M.A.J. Wansapala,¹ T.M.S.G. Tennakoon,² and P.W.D. Thakshila^{1*}

¹ Department of Food Science and Technology, University of Sri Jayewardenepura,
Nugegoda, Sri Lanka

² Research and Development Centre, Link Natural Products (Pvt) Ltd, Malinda, Kapugoda,
Sri Lanka

Ayurvedic arishta is self-fermented polyherbal formulation and Nimba arishta is a widely used ayurvedic drug. According to ayurvedic pharmacopoeia, there are two formulae for making Nimba arishta. The absence of specific recipe or ingredient information on the label of commercially available Nimba arishta, creates a false perception of uniformity among these products within the market. The present study was aimed to evaluate variations in different formulations using six different commercially available brands of Nimba arishta (A, B, C, D, E, and F). They were thoroughly evaluated for their organoleptic characteristics, physicochemical parameters, and antioxidant activity. A sensory evaluation on taste and odour attributes was also performed. The physicochemical parameters evaluated were pH, specific gravity, brix, refractive index, total ash, acid insoluble ash, water-soluble ash, reducing sugar content, sucrose content, alcohol content, total dissolved solid content, total phenolic content, and total flavonoid contents. *In vitro* antioxidant activity was performed by DPPH assay. The results of the study were found within following ranges: pH 3.01(D)–3.64(A), refractive index 1.3725 (A)–1.4019(C), specific gravity 1.0684(A)–1.0864(F), brix 25.06(A)–41.00(C), ethanol content (V/V %) 7.65(C)–10.4(A), total dissolved solids (g/mL) 0.1993(A)–0.4107(C), reducing sugar content (g /100g sample) 15.75(A)–34.24(C), apparent sucrose content (g/100g sample) 0.69(B)–7.69(E), total ash content (w/w%) 0.0971(D)–0.1070(A), water soluble ash content (w/w%)(0.004(B)–0.0899(F), acid insoluble ash content (w/w%) 0.0131(D)–F-0.0571(F), total phenolic content (tannic acid equivalents in mg/g of sample) 1.7275(A)–9.727(F), total flavonoid content (quercetin equivalents in mg/g of sample) 1.2410(A)–3.2151(B), and DPPH radical scavenging activity (IC₅₀) (µg/mL) 35.76(F)–48.04(A). These results indicate that variations in formulae including differences in ingredients, source of herbs or plants, and their quantities, may account for the significant difference observed among different brands. Data obtained in the present study emphasize the need for standardized arishtas in order to enhance the effectiveness and acceptance of these ayurvedic medicines.

Keywords: Nimba arishta, standardization, ayurvedic, physicochemical, antioxidant

E-mail: pwdishanithakshila@gmail.com